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Luminal A and Luminal B bifurcation supported by DBF4 activation in the luminal B subtype.

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We conducted an expression screen to identify genes required for fate choice during subtype selection. We discovered specific activation of two zinc finger nuclear factors, DBF4 and DBF4B, in the luminal B subtype. DBF4 and DBF4B likely support luminal B subtype selection.